

USING MOBILE PHONES TO IMPROVE WATER SERVICE LEVELS IN UGANDA

AN AGENT BASED MODELLING APPROACH

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PREFACE

This report was written during the TU Delft Master course Agent Based Modelling of Complex Adaptive Systems – Advanced (SPM9555). The goal of the course is to let students experience the entire process of creating an agent based model. As both writers of this report did not have any prior experience with agent based modelling and the data analysis package R, the experienced learning curve was steep but in the end the course has definitely reached its goals.

The writers would like to thank our first supervisor and problem owner Deirdre Casella, the experts that provided valuable feedback during the expert validation meeting and the instructors of the course, Igor Nikolic and Andrew Bollinger.

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1. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND ACTOR IDENTIFICATION

This section introduces the problem, the stakeholders involved and the modellers' role within the problem area.

1.1. PROBLEM ANALYSIS

To ensure sanitation and health requirements, clean drinking water should be available to all world citizens. Although this might not seem like a problem in the Western parts of the world, many developing countries struggle with an unsatisfactory water supply. In Uganda, at any given point in time, 30% of the water infrastructure is non-functional. This causes issues to especially rural populations, as they do not have clean alternative sources within their proximity and often turn to non-official sources like rivers and lakes, spreading diseases like diarrhoea and cholera.

To act appropriately, Water Service Providers on all organisational levels require real-time information about the functioning of the water infrastructure as this gives information about the service levels of the users surrounding the infrastructure (IRC, 2013a). An innovative approach to facilitate information diffusion has recently been implemented in some provinces in Uganda. Water users are able to report issues with their water supply using their mobile phones. These issues are stored in a central database, which is accessible to actors throughout the entire water supply hierarchy. This information allows national monitoring of overall service and at the same time provides local decision makers with information that can be used to focus resources more adequately. The system is called Mobiles 4 Water (M4W).

The lack of insight that needs to be addressed is the poor understanding of why the M4W system does not meet the desired results on a communal level and how the effectiveness of the system can be improved.

The system should work as follows: if a user finds a non-functional water point, he uses his mobile phone to send a sms message with the unique id of the water point to the central system. This central system stores the information and makes it available to all users of the system. Hand pump mechanics (HPMs) or their associations are also connected to the system. With the knowledge of a non-functional water point a HPM travels to the water point, fixes the issue and gets paid by the water points' water user committee (WUC, responsible for regular maintenance and operational expenses). The WUCs collect a monthly fee from their water users to fund the expenses (IRC, 2013b).

However, the system does not function in the way it was intended. Currently, water users are not using the sms/calling service often enough for issues to get to the central system in a timely manner. Besides, the WUCs do not collect water user fees on a regular basis. This results in the fact that if information reaches the central system and a hand pump mechanic (HPM) comes to fix the issue; there is no money to pay for the repairs. As the HPM needs to cover his expenses, he leaves without fixing the water point.

The initial hypothesis is that water users have a negative attitude towards having to pay for water as it is seen as a natural resource. Because of the lack of knowledge about the dangers of using dirty water sources, people will defer to dirty sources if their water point is not functioning. As a consequence, WUCs have low incomes and are then not able to maintain the water point, making even less people inclined to pay for water services, because "it is not working anyways".

1.2. PROBLEM OWNER ANALYSIS

The International Water and Sanitation Centre (IRC) has a project Triple-S (Sustainable Services at Scale) that is implementing the Mobiles for Water (M4W) in two districts in Uganda. For this project the IRC is collaborating with SNV Uganda, WaterAid, Makerere University and the Rural Water Department of the Ugandan Ministry of Water and Environment. This consortium of actors and organisations involved in M4W seeks insights into the drivers and hindrances to the M4W monitoring system becoming fully functional.

This report is supervised by Deirdre Casella, an employee of the IRC and currently doing a PhD research at the Delft University of Technology.

The other actors, involved in using the M4W system, are the water user committees (WUCs), hand pump mechanics (HPMs), water users and the district water officer (DWO, responsible for large maintenance) (IRC, 2012).

1.3. ROLE OF THE MODELLER

The role of the modellers is to create a formal computer simulated model based on the system existing in the real world. This model is used to gain more insights into the problems presented above.

2. SYSTEM IDENTIFICATION AND DECOMPOSITION

This section describes how the system in which the problem occurs is composed. The first subsection describes the relevant actors and their properties after which the interactions between the actors are discussed. Finally the environment (external factors that influence the agents but cannot be influenced by the agents) is described.

2.1. INVENTORY

From the problem analysis presented in the previous section, a number of concepts, actors and behaviours emerged. This is essentially the core of the model that will be created. They are stated below:

- The concepts on which the model will be based on are: the preferences for clean water, the attitude towards having to pay for water and the trust in other actors dependent on previous transactions.
- Actors are: water users, Water User Committees (WUCs), Hand Pump Mechanics (HPMs) and the District Water Officer (DWO). Other agents (that are not actors in real life but are modelled as agents are: waterpoints (clean) and water sources (dirty).
- Behaviours are: using water, paying for water, talking to people about water services, fixing water points, paying for repairs and installing new hand pumps
- Interactions are: talking to others, payments for water and repairs, reporting about issues to HPMs
- States properties are: bank balances, water service levels, attitudes towards other agents (primarily for transactions), preferences for water, knowledge about sources, status (functional/non-functional)

2.2. AGENTS

The concepts describes above need to be transformed into agents that have properties and can perform actions and interactions.

Water users have:

- Income
- Money balance
- Willingness to pay
- Time of last payment
- Mobile phone
- Responsible WUC
- Attitude towards their WUC
- Preference for clean waterpoints
- Knowledge about waterpoints and water sources
- A source that he is currently using
- Water service level
- Knowledge about past service levels
- Stubbornness

- Social network

Water user (inter)actions:

- Use water
- Pay for water
- Let HPM know about breakdowns
- Let social network know about functional/non-functional sources

WUCs have:

- Money balance
- Users they are responsible for
- Waterpoints they are responsible for
- Monthly fee
- Performance (average service level of users)

WUCs (inter)actions:

- Collect money
- Pay HPMs for assessment
- Ask HPMs for repairs
- Pay HPMs for repairs

HPMs have:

- Money balance
- Attitude towards WUCs
- Attitude change rate
- Negative experience bias
- Favourite job
- Assessment fee
- Knowledge about waterpoints
- Social network

HPMs (inter)actions:

- Assess waterpoints
- Fix waterpoints
- Receive money for assessments

DWOs have:

- Income
- Budget for major repairs
- Budget for new waterpoints
- Knowledge about service levels of users

DWO (inter)actions:

- Pay for major repairs
- Install new waterpoints
- Pay for new waterpoints

Waterpoints (clean) have:

- Type
- Construction cost
- Cost of repairs
- Time between breakdowns
- Water quality
- Status (functional/non-functional)
- Type of breakdown (minor/major)
- Breakdown assessed by HPM
- Water users

Water sources (dirty) have:

- Water quality
- Status
- Water users

2.3. CONCEPT OF TIME

The interest of this modelling project lies in the daily interactions between actors on a community level. People in rural parts of Uganda make the trip to their water point on at least a daily basis. Therefore the decision was made to regards one 'tick' in the model as one day.

2.4. USER SERVICE LEVEL ADJUSTMENTS

The water service level of the users was initially assumed to vary as a linear function of the distance to their waterpoint. However, after discussions with the problem owner, the calculation was adjusted to reflect the non-linearity of water collection quantity as a function of distance. As presented in the table and graph below, water consumption typically follows a rough plateau for distances between 100m and 1000m (or a travel time of 5 to 30 minutes).

Table 1: Health-based requirements for water service level (Howard, Bartram, & others, 2003)

Service level	Access measure	Needs met	Level of health concern
No access (quantity collected often below 5 l/c/d)	More than 1000m or 30 minutes total collection time	Consumption – cannot be assured Hygiene – not possible (unless practised at source)	Very high
Basic access (average quantity unlikely to exceed 20 l/c/d)	Between 100 and 1000m or 5 to 30 minutes total collection time	Consumption – should be assured Hygiene – handwashing and basic food hygiene possible; laundry/bathing difficult to assure unless carried out at source	High
Intermediate access (average quantity about 50 l/c/d)	Water delivered through one tap on-plot (or within 100m or 5 minutes total collection time)	Consumption – assured Hygiene – all basic personal and food hygiene assured; laundry and bathing should also be assured	Low
Optimal access (average quantity 100 l/c/d and above)	Water supplied through multiple taps continuously	Consumption – all needs met Hygiene – all needs should be met	Very low

Figure 2-1: Daily water consumption per capita as a function of travel time (WHO, 2003)

In the rural context described by the model, the significant increase in water collection provided by “on-plot” service is less relevant; the data was also adjusted to reflect the minimum service level definition given for Uganda by Nimanya, Nabunnya, Kyeyune, & Heijnen (2011), in which the minimum service level corresponds to clean water within 1.5 km. As represented in the model, the service level is thus quantitatively approximated as follows:

Table 2: Adjusted water service level calculation in the model

	Distance (m)	Service level rating
No service	> 1500	0
Intermediate	1000	0.5
Full service	< 100	1

The calculation was implemented as a simple quadratic curve fit in the model. However, given the importance of this indicator, further work should incorporate more detailed data about water collection in local conditions - including an explicit treatment of the quantity of water gathered by each user.

2.5. ENVIRONMENT AND SPATIAL LAYOUT

The environment consists of things that do have influence on the agents but the agents cannot influence:

- Gives all agents a location (which influences the distance between users and waterpoints and sources and gives all waterpoints a WUC)
- Creates social network of the water users and HPMs
- Gives income to the water users and DWO
- Generates different types of waterpoints (with different properties)
- Lets waterpoints break down

Given the context of the model, the actions and interactions of the agents have a clear spatial dependence: HPMs physically move from waterpoint to waterpoint, while the service level and waterpoint choice of water users is affected by their geographic distribution. The size and layout of the environment will therefore play a major role in determining the outcomes of the model. After discussing with the problem owner, an appropriate geographic boundary was chosen by focusing on an area representative of the eastern half of Rwiimi subcounty, in Uganda’s Kabarole District.

Kabarole was one of the districts selected for a pilot implementation of the M4W system; as of 2010, Rwiimi subcounty presented the lowest access rate in the district, with 69% of the population having access to point water sources (Ministry of Water & Environment, 2010). This may be explained by the poor ground water potential in the area, which affects the technical and economic feasibility of new waterpoints. From left to right, the figure below shows Kabarole’s location in Uganda, and Rwiimi’s location within the district.

Figure 2-2: Geographical layout of the model environment (Uganda Ministry of Water & Environment, 2010)

The table below summarizes water service data for the subcounty (Ministry of Water & Environment, 2010). Given the computational and data requirements that would be involved in a full simulation of the subcounty, it was decided to further subdivide the subcounty (which covers an approximate area of 77 km² with 28,000 inhabitants). A square area of 36 km² was thus selected with the same average density of water users and waterpoints of each type.

Table 3: Water service level for Rwiimi subcounty in Kabarole district (Uganda Ministry of Water & Environment, 2010)

Admin Unit	Population	Population served	Point Water Sources										
			% access		Protected springs			Shallow wells			Deep boreholes		
			Rural	Rural	Functional	Non functional	Total	Functional	Non functional	Total	Functional	Non functional	Total
RWIIMI	28,300	16,948	69	77	10	1	11	16	6	22	3	5	8

Furthermore, in order to limit the number of agents in the simulation, the water users were chosen to represent small neighbourhoods of 5 households of 5 persons each, which would themselves be clustered in a random arrangement of “villages”. The baseline spatial conceptualization was therefore intended to simulate 540 water users, corresponding to a population of 13,500 persons. This population would then be served by 20 waterpoints proportionally distributed between each type of point water source. Finally, the location parameters would be adjusted to obtain a realistic initial access rate.

This method for setting up the environment is intended as a first approach to modelling the dynamics of the system; given the importance of geographic parameters in the context of water services in general, and M4W in particular, a full subcounty-level simulation should preferably be integrated with GIS data in order to accurately represent waterpoint locations and population clusters.

3. CONCEPT FORMALISATION

As the data structures need to be known before starting to program, the properties and objects defined in the previous section need to be formalised below.

Water users have:

Variable	Type	Range
Income	Floating point	≥ 0
Money balance	Floating point	≥ 0
Willingness to pay	Floating point	≥ 0
Time of last payment	Integer	≥ 0
Mobile phone	Boolean	
Responsible WUC	Agent	
Attitude towards their WUC	Floating point	≥ 0 and ≤ 1
Preference for clean waterpoints	Floating point	≥ 0 and ≤ 1
Knowledge about waterpoints and water sources	Table	C1: waterpoints/sources C2: status
A source that he is currently using	Agent	
Water service level	Floating point	≥ 0
Knowledge about past service levels	List of floating points	≥ 0
Stubbornness	Integer	> 0
Long term orientation	Integer	> 0
Social network	Links with users and HPMs	

Water User Committees have:

Variable	Type	Range
Money balance	Floating point	≥ 0
Users they are responsible for	List of agents	
Waterpoints they are responsible for	List of agents	
Monthly fee	Integer	≥ 0
Performance (average service level of users)	Floating point	≥ 0

Hand pump mechanics have:

Variable	Type	Range
Money balance	Floating point	≥ 0
Attitude towards WUCs	Table	C1: WUCs, C2: attitude (floating point, ≥ 0 and ≤ 1)
Attitude change rate	Floating point	≥ 0
Negative experience bias	Floating point	≥ 0

Favourite job	Agent	
Assessment fee	Integer	≥ 0
Knowledge about waterpoints	Table	C1: waterpoints, C2: status)
Social network	Links with users and HPMs	

District water officers have:

Variable	Type	Range
Income	Integer	≥ 0
Budget for major repairs	Floating point	≥ 0
Budget for new waterpoints	Floating point	≥ 0

Waterpoints have:

Variable	Type	Range
Type	Integer	0, 1, 2
Construction cost	Integer	≥ 0
Cost of repairs	Integer	≥ 0
Time between breakdowns	Integer	≥ 0
Water quality	Floating point	≥ 0 and ≤ 1
Status (functional/non-functional)	Boolean	0, 1
Type of breakdown	Boolean	0, 1
Breakdown assessed	Boolean	0, 1
Water users	Integer	≥ 0

Water sources have:

Variable	Type	Range
Water quality	Floating point	≥ 0 and ≤ 1
Status	Boolean	0, 1
Water users	Integer	≥ 0

4. MODEL FORMALISATION

The next steps include writing the model narrative (who does what when?) and using the narrative to create a pseudo code. Both the narrative and pseudo code are presented in the sections below. Throughout the modelling project they have been iteratively kept up to date with new developments in implementation.

4.1. MODEL NARRATIVE

The model narrative is in essence an easily readable, but detailed, description about what happens in the model between every 'tick'.

4.1.1. Water users narrative

Get up, drink a cup of coffee and then... NO! There is no coffee because there is no water! Therefore we need to do the following:

4.1.2. Initial environment setup

A water service delivery area is described with:

- A given number of population clusters is distributed randomly on the grid, with users distributed randomly within a given maximum radius of the centre of each cluster. This loosely represents the geographical distribution of villages at a sub-subcounty level
- A given number of waterpoints is distributed randomly between population clusters, and located within a given maximum radius of each cluster
- A given number of non-improved water sources is distributed randomly on the grid
- WUCs are created sequentially at the location of each waterpoint that is not already covered by the activity radius of an existing WUC
- A given number of HPMs is created at a location adjacent to a random population cluster
- DWO is created at a random location (its geographical location being irrelevant)
- Set up agent properties for water users, water user committees, HPM, DWO, waterpoints and water sources
- Set up social network of users and HPM, based on a given number of desired total links and a desired fraction of global links with users beyond a given radius. The social network setup follows the work from Holzhauser, Krebs and Ernst (2012) who describe an algorithm that lets agents pair up with a group of agents that live fairly close as well as a few more distant agents.

4.1.3. Water users' narrative

1. Receive daily income from environment and updates money balance
2. Travel to waterpoint or other source based on knowledge about working waterpoints, distance to waterpoints, and attitude towards other sources
 - a. If waterpoint is broken: Update knowledge about working waterpoints
 - b. Decide on going to another waterpoint or other water source, based on attitude towards water from other sources
 - c. If water source is working, tap water and leave

With the M4W policy, if a non-functional waterpoint was found:

3. *Decide on reporting the breakdown through a SMS/call with the M4W system, based on willingness to pay, mobile phone ownership, attitude towards WUC*
4. *If unable/unwilling to pay, decide on letting WUC know about the non-functional waterpoint based on attitude towards WUC; the WUC is then assumed to automatically report the waterpoint in the M4W system*
5. Update user's service level based on the water quality of the source, the distance to the source, and whether or not it is overcrowded compared to the average number of users per waterpoint
6. Interact with a given fraction of user's social network, letting them know about the status of the priority source, and about the status of another randomly chosen waterpoint known to be broken
7. Update attitude towards WUC based on three components:
 - a. External attitude change is based on the difference between the average attitude of the user's social network and their own attitude, divided by the user's stubbornness
 - b. Internal attitude change is based on the sum of an absolute perception component (taking the difference between the user's current service level and the initial median service level of all users in the subcounty), and a relative perception component (with the difference between the user's current service level, and the average of remembered past service levels over a given "memory"). Both components are then divided by the user's long-term orientation, which dampens the rate of change.
8. Pay WUC based on the basic maximum willingness to pay, user's income relative to the population average, WUC fees, attitude towards WUC, and preference for waterpoints

4.1.4. Waterpoints' narrative

1. Each day, calculate the time elapsed since the last minor and major breakdowns, and determine whether or not to break down based on a Weibull distribution with a given shape parameter, and median durations between minor and major breakdowns

4.1.5. Water User Committees' narrative

- If water user reports break down:
 - Report issue to HPM by indicating that the waterpoint is ready to assess (covered in action 1.4)
- 1. Recalculate the average service level of users under the WUC's responsibility
- 2. Upon request of HPM for payment for assessment :
 - a. When balance is high enough: pay for assessment
- 3. Upon request of HPM for payment of a minor repair:
 - a. When balance is high enough: pay for repair
- 4. If a non-functional waterpoint under the WUC's responsibility was previously assessed but left unrepaired due to a lack of funds, and the WUC has successfully raised enough funds for the repair:
 - a. Inform HPM that waterpoint is ready to be reassessed and repaired

4.1.6. Hand pump mechanic's narrative

1. Receive breakdown alert from M4W system or notification of a breakdown through the HPM's social network; choose a priority repair job to respond to, based on distance and attitude towards WUC responsible.
2. Respond to priority repair job (if any) and travel to the waterpoint
3. When arriving:
 - a. Determine type of failure and, in the case of a minor breakdown that can be repaired by the HPM, the cost for repair:
 - i. Ask the WUC whether it has sufficient money to pay for the assessment
 1. If WUC has sufficient money balance:
 - a. Assess the waterpoint and positively adjust the HPM's attitude towards the WUC
 2. If WUC has insufficient money balance:
 - a. Still assess the waterpoint, but negatively adjust attitude towards the WUC
4. If the waterpoint needs repairs for a major breakdown (too complex to fix immediately by the HPM):
 - a. Report major breakdown to DWO
5. If the waterpoint has a minor issue and can be repaired by the HPM:
 - i. Ask WUC about further action:
 1. If WUC decides to repair:
 - a. Repair issue
 - b. Receive payment
 - c. Inform users that the waterpoint has been repaired
 2. If WUC decides not to repair: do nothing
6. Adjust attitude towards WUC positively or negatively, based on the outcome of the repair interaction
7. Go to next repair job on the HPM's list

4.1.7. District water officers' narrative

1. DWO receives a given income every 90 days (to simulate a quarterly release of funds corresponding to the District Water and Sanitation Conditional Grant), with a certain percentage being allocated towards the rehabilitation of existing sources
 2. If HPM has reported major breakdown:
 - a. Check available repair funds
 - i. If available funds are greater than the rehabilitation cost of one or more waterpoints with a major breakdown:
 1. Basic policy: Pick the broken waterpoint which has the lowest rehabilitation cost; ask WUC responsible to contribute an amount equivalent to the cost of a minor repair (or its money balance if funds are insufficient). Repair the waterpoint and inform users about the rehabilitation.
 2. Alternate policy: Prioritize the broken waterpoint which belongs to the WUC with the lowest average service level, but which the DWO can still afford to repair; proceed with repairs as with the basic policy
- An additional component was initially proposed to represent the DWO building new waterpoints, with a randomly chosen waterpoint "project" being proposed each quarter, and built if DWO funds were sufficient. However, after discussing with the problem owner, this

routine was not implemented for the experiment runs in order to reduce the amount of exogenous factors in the model and simplify the interpretation of results.

The decision structure presented in Figure 4-1 summarizes the decision rules for all actors involved in the model.

Figure 4-1: The graphical representation of the model narrative

4.2. PSEUDO-CODE

After specifying the model narrative, the actions of the agents need to be translated into pseudo-code. Pseudo-code is a human readable form of code without any computer language specific elements; it forms the step between the narrative and the software implementation. The following sections display the created pseudo-code. Since the model was intended to be programmed with NetLogo, the pseudo-code closely follows the actual programming syntax of the software.

4.2.1. DECLARATIONS

users own:

- income
- mobile-phone
- money-balance
- attitude-towards-wuc
- preference-for-waterpoints
- knowledge-about-sources
- priority-source
- service-level
- dailywateruse
- wuc-responsible
- paid-this-month
- long-term-orientation
- stubbornness
- list-of-past-service-levels
- time-of-last-payment
- willingness-to-pay

waterpoints own:

- waterpoint-type
- construction-cost
- cost-of-major-repair
- cost-of-minor-repair
- major-breakdown-interval
- minor-breakdown-interval
- major-breakdown-flag
- water-quality
- status
- wuc-responsible
- current-users
- breakdown-assessed
- breakdown-reported
- time-of-minor-breakdown
- time-of-major-breakdown
- downtime

watersources own:

- water-quality
- status
- current-users

HPMs own:

- mobile-phone
- money-balance
- list-of-attitudes-towards-wucs
- attitude-increment
- negative-experience-bias
- priority-job
- rate-for-assessment
- home-xlocation
- home-ylocation
- knowledge-about-sources

WUCs own:

- money-balance
- total-users
- paying-users
- waterpoints-managed
- monthly-payment
- average-service-level

DWOs own:
 income
 money-balance-for-repair
 money-balance-for-new-waterpoints
 percentage-of-funds-for-new-waterpoints
 percentage-of-funds-for-repair

4.2.2. SETUP

```

to setup
  set random seed
  setup-watersources
  setup-users
  setup-waterpoints
  setup-WUCs
  setup-HPM
  setup-DWO
  setup-social-network
  setup-globals
end

to setup-globals
  set cost-of-sms to 220
  set initial-mean-service-level to report-initial-mean-service-level
end

to setup waterpoints
  ask waterpoints to:
    rotate by random 360
    move forward by random max-waterpoint-distance
    let random-type to random 100
    ifelse random-type >= 90 ;10% chance of borehole
      [ set waterpoint-type 0 ]
    [ ifelse random-type >= 40 ;50% chance of well
      [ set waterpoint-type 1 ]
      [ set waterpoint-type 2] ;40% chance of spring
    ]
    init-waterpoint-properties
    let random-status to random 100
    ifelse random-status >= 70
      [ set status 0 ]
      [ set status 1 ]
end

to setup-watersources
  create a number of dirty water sources equal to number-of-waterpoints * fraction-of-dirty-watersources and ask them to:
    set position to random-xcor random-ycor
    set water-quality to 0
    set status to 1
end

to setup-users
  create a number of "seed" users equal to number-of-population-clusters and ask them to:
    set position to random-xcor random-ycor
  while [count waterpoints < number-of-waterpoints]
    [ ask one of the "seed" users to create a waterpoint ]
  ask users to create a number of users equal to users-per-cluster - 1, and ask them to:
    rotate by random 360
    move forward by random max-radius-from-cluster

    set service-level to 0
    set paid-this-month to 0
    set income to a randomly distributed value with mu = 3300 and sigma = 500
    set money-balance to random 5000
    set willingness-to-pay to income / 3300 * 5 * base-willingness-to-pay

    let random-phone to random 100
    ifelse random-phone >= 80
      [ set mobile-phone 0 ]
      [ set mobile-phone 1 ]

    set preference-for-waterpoints to random-float 1
    set attitude-towards-wuc to 0.5
    set long-term-orientation to 100 + random 50

```

```

    set stubbornness to 1 + random 50
    set list-of-past-service-levels to an empty list

    create table for knowledge-about-sources, with keys equal to IDs of waterpoints and watersources
    set all values in knowledge-about-sources to 1
end

to setup-social-network
  let ChanceForGlobalLink 0.2
  let total-links 15
  let local-radius 10
  find all users that don't have the specified number of social-links ask one of those users to:
    while social-links < 15 [
      create social link with someone within 1 km that also doesn't have 15 social-links yet
      if RandomNumber < ChanceForGlobalLink [
        create social link with someone that doesn't have 15 links yet is farther than 1 km away ]]
    end
end

to setup-WUCs
  ask waterpoints that do not have a WUC within max-radius-for-wuc to create a WUC
  ask waterpoints to set their wuc-responsible to the nearest WUC
  ask users to set their wuc-responsible to the wuc-responsible of the nearest waterpoint
  ask WUCs to:
    set waterpoints-managed to waterpoints with wuc-responsible = myself
    set total-users to users with wuc-responsible = myself
    set monthly-payment to wuc-monthly-payment * 5
    set money-balance to 10000
end

to setup-HPM
  ask a number of waterpoints equal to number-of-HPMs to create a HPM
  ask HPMs to:
    create table for list-of-attitudes-towards-WUCs, with keys equal to IDs of WUCs
    set all values in list-of-attitudes-towards-WUCs to 1
    create table for knowledge-about-sources, with keys equal to IDs of waterpoints and watersources
    set all values in knowledge-about-sources to 1
    set money-balance to random 5000
    set rate-for-assessment to 2500
    set attitude-increment to 0.2
    set negative-experience-bias to 1.5
    set home-xlocation xcor
    set home-ylocation ycor
end

to setup-DWO
  create one DWO and ask it to:
    set income to 30000 * number of users
    set money-balance-for-repair to 0
    set money-balance-for-new-waterpoints to 0
    set percentage-of-funds-for-new-waterpoints to 0.7
    set percentage-of-funds-for-repair to 0.13
end

```

4.2.3. RUN PROCEDURES

```

to go
  ask users to:
    receive-income
    set dailywateruse FALSE
    while [dailywateruse = FALSE][fetch-water]

  ask waterpoints and watersources to set their current-users to the number of users who are linked with them
  ask users to:
    set service-level to the result of report-service-level
    update-attitude-towards-wuc
    pay-for-water
  ask HPMs to:
    setxy home-xlocation home-ylocation
    respond-to-job
  ask WUCs to:
    request-fix

```

```

        set paying-users to the number of users with wuc-responsible = myself and paid-this-month = 1
        set average-service-level to the mean service-level of users with wuc-responsible = myself
    ask DWOs to run dwo-operations procedure
    ask waterpoints to run breakdown procedure
    increment ticks
end

```

4.2.3.1. USER PROCEDURES

```

to receive-income
    set money-balance to money-balance + income * (0.5 + random-float 1)
end

to fetch-water
    delete existing priority-link
    set priority-source to the result of report-priority-source
    create a priority link with priority-source
    ifelse [status] of priority-source = 1
        [set dailywateruse to TRUE]
        [if M4W = TRUE and ticks > 180 [report-issue]]

    update knowledge-about-sources at the key corresponding to the ID of priority-source, with the value of priority-source's status
    let knowledge-distribution to any waterpoint in knowledge-about-sources with status = 0
        ask a fraction of my social link neighbors equal to daily-social-interaction to:
            update knowledge-about-sources at the key corresponding to the ID of priority-source, with the value of priority-source's status
            update knowledge-about-sources at the key corresponding to the ID of knowledge-distribution, with 0
    end

to report-issue
    ifelse (mobile-phone * willingness-to-pay * attitude-towards-wuc > cost-of-sms )
        [ ask priority-source to set breakdown-reported to 1 ]
        [ if (attitude-towards-wuc > 0.5) [ ask priority-source to set breakdown-reported to 1 ] ]
    end

to update-attitude-towards-wuc
    ifelse list-of-past-service-levels is empty
        [set list-of-past-service-levels to service-level]
        [ if ticks mod 10 = 0
            [ifelse length of list-of-past-service-levels < long-term-orientation / 10
                [add service-level to the end of list-of-past-service-levels]
                [add service-level to the end of list-of-past-service-levels and remove the first value]]
            ]
        set internal-attitude-change to (effect-of-relative-perception * (service-level - mean list-of-past-service-levels) + effect-of-absolute-
        perception * (service-level - initial-mean-service-level)) / long-term-orientation
        set external-attitude-change to effect-of-social-network * (mean attitude-towards-wuc of social link neighbors - attitude-towards-
        wuc) / stubbornness
        set attitude-towards-wuc to attitude-towards-wuc + internal-attitude-change + external-attitude-change, within an interval of 0 to 1
    end

to pay-for-water
    if ( ticks > time-of-last-payment + 30)
        [
            set paid-this-month to 0
            if(willingness-to-pay * attitude-towards-wuc * preference-for-waterpoints > monthly-payment of wuc-responsible)
                [ set money-balance money-balance - monthly-payment of wuc-responsible
                    ask wuc-responsible to set its money-balance to money-balance + monthly-payment
                    set time-of-last-payment ticks
                    set paid-this-month 1 ]
        ]
    end

```

4.2.3.2. HPM PROCEDURES

```

to respond-to-job
    set priority-job to the result of report-priority-job
    if status of priority-job = 0 and breakdown-assessed of priority-job = 0
        [ move-to priority-job
            ifelse money-balance of wuc-responsible of priority-job > rate-for-assessment
                [
                    ask wuc-responsible of priority-job to:
                    set money-balance to money-balance - rate-for-assessment
                    ask priority-job to set breakdown-assessed to 1
                    set money-balance to money-balance + rate-for-assessment
                ]
        ]
    end

```

```

    update list-of-attitudes-towards-wucs at the key corresponding to the ID of WUC, adding the value of attitude-increment
  ]
  [
    ask priority-job to set breakdown-assessed to 1
    update list-of-attitudes-towards-wucs at the key corresponding to the ID of WUC, subtracting the value of attitude-
    increment * negative-experience-bias
  ]
  if major-breakdown of priority-job = 0
    [ifelse money-balance of wuc-responsible of priority-job > cost-of-minor-repair of priority-job
      [
        ask wuc-responsible of priority-job to:
        set money-balance to money-balance - cost-of-minor-repair of priority-job
        ask priority-job to:
          set status 1
          set breakdown-reported 0
          set breakdown-assessed 0
          set DT ticks - time-of-minor-breakdown
          set time-of-minor-breakdown ticks
        update knowledge-about-sources at the key corresponding to the ID of priority-job, with 1
        ask users to update their knowledge-about-sources at the key corresponding to the ID of priority-job, with 1
        update list-of-attitudes-towards-wucs at the key corresponding to the ID of WUC, adding the value of attitude-
        increment
      ]
      [
        update list-of-attitudes-towards-wucs at the key corresponding to the ID of WUC, subtracting the value of
        attitude-increment * negative-experience-bias
      ]
    ]
  ]
end

```

4.2.3.3. WUC PROCEDURES

```

to request-fix
  let waterpoints-waiting-for-repair to waterpoints-managed with breakdown-assessed = 1 and major-breakdown = 0 and cost-of-
  minor-repair < money-balance of myself
  if there are any waterpoints waiting for repair:
    [let priority-repair to the waterpoints-waiting-for-repair with the smallest cost-of-minor-repair
      ask priority-repair to set breakdown-assessed to 0]
end

```

4.2.3.4. WATERPOINT PROCEDURES

```

to breakdown
  let overuse-factor to maximum of current-users / initial-mean-users-per-waterpoint, or 1
  if status = 1 [
    set minor-breakdown-threshold to a conditional failure rate drawn from a Weibull distribution with x = (ticks - time-of-minor-
    breakdown) and a = minor-breakdown-interval
    set major-breakdown-threshold to a conditional failure rate drawn from a Weibull distribution with x = (ticks - time-of-major-
    breakdown) and a = major-breakdown-interval
    let random-breakdown random-float 1
    if random-breakdown <= major-breakdown-threshold * overuse-factor
      [ set status to 0
        set major-breakdown to 1
        set time-of-major-breakdown to ticks]
    if random-breakdown <= (minor-breakdown-threshold + major-breakdown-threshold) * overuse-factor
      [ set status to 0
        set time-of-minor-breakdown to ticks]
  ]
end

```

to init-waterpoint-properties
According to waterpoint-type, assign the following properties:

Property	waterpoint-type		
	0 (Borehole)	1 (Well)	2 (Protected spring)
construction-cost	20,000,000	6,000,000	2,500,000
cost-of-major-repair	2,750,000	1,600,000	750,000

cost-of-minor-repair	90,000	100,000	125,000
major-breakdown-interval	1,825	1,825	1,825
minor-breakdown-interval	60	60	60
water-quality	1	1	1

```

set breakdown-assessed to 0
set breakdown-reported to 0
end

```

4.2.3.5. DWO PROCEDURES

```

to dwo-operations
  if ticks mod 90 = 0
    [set money-balance-for-repair to money-balance-for-repair + income * percentage-of-funds-for-repair / 4
    set money-balance-for-new-waterpoints to money-balance-for-new-waterpoints + income * percentage-of-funds-for-new-waterpoints / 4]

    let waterpoints-waiting-for-major-repair to (waterpoints with breakdown-assessed = 1 and major-breakdown = 1 and cost-of-major-repair < money-balance-for-repair of myself)

    if there are any waterpoints-waiting-for-major-repair:
      let priority-repair to waterpoints-waiting-for-major-repair with the smallest cost-of-major-repair
      ;let priority-repair to waterpoints-waiting-for-major-repair with the smallest average-service-level of wuc-responsible
      let community-contribution minimum of cost-of-minor-repair of priority-repair, or money-balance of wuc-responsible
      set money-balance-for-repair to money-balance-for-repair - cost-of-major-repair of priority-repair + community-contribution
      ask wuc-responsible of priority-repair to set money-balance to money-balance - community-contribution
      ask priority-repair to:
        set status to 1
        set major-breakdown to 0
        set breakdown-reported to 0
        set breakdown-assessed to 0
        set time-of-major-breakdown to ticks
        set time-of-minor-breakdown to ticks
      ask users to update their knowledge-about-sources at the key corresponding to the ID of priority-job, with 1
    end
end

```

4.2.3.6. REPORT PROCEDURES

```

to-report report-service-level
  report water-quality of priority-source * (-2.0E-3 * distance to priority-source ^ 2 - 0.035 * distance to priority-source + 1) / (current-users of priority-source / initial-mean-users-per-waterpoint)
end

to-report report-priority-source
  report waterpoint or watersource with the maximum of [1 / distance from myself * (1 - (1 - water-quality) * preference-for-waterpoints of myself) * my knowledge-about-sources of the source]
end

to-report report-priority-job
  ifelse M4W = TRUE and ticks > 180
  [report waterpoint with maximum of [1 / distance from myself * value from list-of-attitude-towards-WUCs at ID of WUC responsible * breakdown-reported * (1 - breakdown-assessed)]]
  [report waterpoint with maximum of [1 / distance from myself * value from list-of-attitude-towards-WUCs at ID of WUC responsible * (1 - my knowledge-about-sources of the source) * (1 - breakdown-assessed)]]
end

```

5. SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION

To transform the model narrative and pseudo code into a working, computer simulated model it has to be implemented into a certain modelling environment. For this project NetLogo¹ was chosen. NetLogo is a free, open source modelling environment developed by Northwestern University. The NetLogo modelling language is relatively easy to comprehend and learn. Furthermore, due to its open source and free character, there is a large community of developers and many example models are distributed with the software.

In total, approximately 750 lines of code have been written. Some of these include extensions of the NetLogo package. First of all, tables² are used for various processes where agents need to remember things. After considering lists and arrays to manage internal data structures, it was decided to use tables for their greater simplicity, as NetLogo's documentation indicates that computational performance should be similar between both types of data structures.

Tables can be used to store information coupled to a 'key'. The key acts like an id does in databases, it can be used to store and call data and has to be unique. Water users use tables to store information about the functioning of waterpoints (using the waterpoint [who] as the key) and the HPM uses a table to store attitude towards the WUCs (using the WUCs [who] as the key). Secondly, the profiler³ extension was used to optimize the model runs. The profiler provides data about the amount of time each routine takes, using this information the model was optimized in an efficient manner.

Another advantage of NetLogo is the ability to graphically represent agent based model in an attractive way. After the setup, the 'world' is represented as shown in Figure 5-1. Green patches form the background of the world, on top of that are the users (small dots), clean waterpoints (flags, red for non-functional and blue for functional), dirty water sources (red crosses), links between the users and their favourite water source (grey lines), the WUCs (yellow dots) and finally the HPM (the tall yellow man). Running the model will show the HPM visiting (and repairing) broken sources, at the same time users who find a broken source change their priority link towards a functioning waterpoint. The user colours can be set to represent water service level or the attitude towards their WUC. The full interface is shown in Appendix A.

The locational setup can be executed with a random seed, however, Figure 5-1 shows the setup with the fixed seed that we used for our experiments as explained in section 6.4.2. The model does give the possibility to change settings like amount of users, amount of clean and dirty water sources, radii around waterpoints and other aspects about the locational setup, but these variables are not used for this report (see section 2.5).

¹ <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/>

² <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/docs/arraystables.html>

³ <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/docs/profiler.html>

Figure 5-1: The graphical output of the model

6. MODEL VERIFICATION

Before being able to use the created model, it has to be determined whether the model as specified in Section 4 has been implemented correctly (see Chapter 0 for implementation). After determining how the agent behaviour will be tracked, subsequent sections will describe the performed tests and the test results.

6.1. RECORDING AND TRACKING AGENT BEHAVIOUR

In order to do further testing it is necessary to follow agent behaviour, for this we need to let agents output information about their behaviour. Therefore we programmed the model in such a way that the agents output important information about their actions, interactions and transactions. Using a debug switch it is possible to turn this output on or off. The following information is given in 'debug-mode':

Procedure / agent	Information output
Social network setup	Report count of users with incomplete networks (social links < maximum links)
	Report count of social links for user with the least links
	Report average total number of social links
	Report average number of distant social links
Users	Report list of past service levels
	Report result of priority source calculation
	Upon encountering a broken waterpoint: report mobile phone ownership, willingness to pay, attitude towards WUC, and decision whether to send SMS, inform WUC, or do nothing
	Upon being asked for payment by WUC: report decision whether or not to pay, and attitude towards WUC
WUCs	Report average service level of users
	Report number of paying users and total users for the current month
	Upon being asked to pay for assessment: report money balance before payment, and after payment if balance is sufficient
	Upon being asked to pay for repair: report money balance before payment, and after payment if balance is sufficient
	Upon raising sufficient funds to repair a previously assessed but unrepaired waterpoint: report money balance and decision to inform HPM
Waterpoints	Upon assessment: report delay between breakdown and arrival of HPM
	Upon breakdown: report time and type of breakdown
HPMs	Upon assessment: report type of breakdown, and cost of repair for a minor breakdown
	Upon interaction with WUC (assessment or repair): report updated attitude towards WUC
DWO	ID and cost of major repair for any waterpoints waiting for major rehabilitation
	Upon fixing a major breakdown: report cost of major repair and community contribution from WUC

These outputs cover the main interactions and decision structures presented in the narrative. They can therefore be used as a tool for the verification of the model, by displaying internal states that may otherwise not be easily captured by the output of the model.

6.2. SINGLE-AGENT TESTING

As a first step for the verification of the model, single-agent testing will focus on exploring the decisions of each type of agent; given the amount of interactions between the different agents, this can help identify errors in the formalization of the model through a modular approach. This section therefore first presents single-agent tests in order to evaluate the behaviour of the agents under expected conditions. For clarity, the testing will be structured following the decision rules previously identified for the narrative.

6.2.1. Water user tests

1. User income: The daily user income should vary in a normally distributed manner, with a given standard deviation around a given average. This can be tested by setting the user's initial money balance to 0, and checking the money balance after one tick. Using values for daily income of 3300 shillings with a standard deviation of 500 shillings, the mean money balance of the 540 users is 3305 shillings after one tick, with a standard deviation of 505. **Confirmed**

2. Select priority source: The users select a priority source which maximizes the following formula, within the agentset of waterpoints and water sources:

$$\frac{1}{Distance} \cdot [1 - (1 - Water\ quality) \cdot Preference\ for\ waterpoints] \cdot Knowledge\ about\ status$$

The formula can be verified by displaying the result of the priority source calculation, and manipulating the inputs to the calculation. The three screenshots below show the priority link established by a given user (circled in red), first using a preference for waterpoints of 0 (which favors the closest water source, in red), then manually increasing the user's preference for waterpoints to 1 (which causes the user to favor the nearest waterpoint), and finally by manually disabling the nearest waterpoint (in which case the user goes to the next nearest waterpoint). In each case, the numerical result of the formula can be verified using the values for distance, water quality, and preference for waterpoints.

In order to handle extreme values (as the distance could theoretically be 0, resulting in a divide by zero error), the denominator of the first term in the equation is adjusted to take the maximum of the actual distance, or 0.1 (i.e. 10 meters).

Confirmed

Figure 6-1: Priority link selection under different cases

3. Directly inform HPM using the M4W system upon encountering a broken waterpoint: This can be verified directly using the debugging function, which is set up to report the user's decision. A sample output is then:

(user 520): "My pump is broken. Mobile phone = 1, willingness to pay = 16427.6428072848 and attitude towards WUC = 0.5424090563023782. So I'm sending an sms"

The user then correspondingly sets the waterpoint's Reported flag to 1. As implemented in the code, the minimum attitude threshold above which the M4W system is used is above 0.5; manually adjusting the user's attitude below 0.5, and running the simulation again with the same random seed, results in the following output:

(user 520): "My pump is broken. Mobile phone = 1, willingness to pay = 16427.6428072848 and attitude towards WUC = 0. So I'm not doing anything"

In this case, the waterpoint's Reported flag is not adjusted by the user. **Confirmed**

4. Inform WUC upon encountering a broken waterpoint: Similarly, the debugging function is used to obtain the following output, for users without a mobile phone and attitudes above and below the threshold of 0.5:

(user 301): "My pump is broken. Mobile phone = 0, money balance = 6493.24866459964 and attitude towards WUC = 0.5491732484627713. So I'm letting the WUC know"

(user 194): "My pump is broken. Mobile phone = 0, money balance = 6726.25179283222 and attitude towards WUC = 0.49486969928572666. So I'm not doing anything"

For each case, the user sets the waterpoint's Reported flag respectively to 1 and 0. **Confirmed**

5. Update service level: The service level calculation can be verified in parallel with the priority source calculation. Using the same configuration displayed in the figure above, the service level increases from 0 to 0.398 as the user switches from a non-improved water source (with a water quality of 0) to a waterpoint, then decreases to 0.310 as the user chooses a more distant waterpoint. This corresponds to the output of the formula for each priority source's quality and distance.

Extreme values are handled by using *min* and *max* functions to saturate the service level between 0 and 1. **Confirmed**

6. Interact with social network: The knowledge exchange interaction is tested in the minimal model verification.

7. Update attitude towards WUC: The attitude is based on three components: external attitude change, absolute perception of the service level, and relative perception. Testing each in turn:

a) The external attitude change is based on the difference between the average attitude of the user's social network and its own attitude, divided by the user's stubbornness. This can then be tested by manipulating the attitude and stubbornness of a given user's social network, as well as the user's own properties, as follows:

```
ask user 297 [ask sociallink-neighbors [set attitude-towards-wuc 1]]
ask user 297 [ask sociallink-neighbors [set stubbornness 10000]]
ask user 297 [set attitude-towards-wuc 0]
ask user 297 [set stubbornness 1]
```

As expected, advancing by one tick then results in the user setting its attitude to 1.

b) The effect of the absolute perception can be tested in isolation by setting the multipliers of the two other components to 0. This component of the attitude change is given by the difference between the user's current service level and the initial median service level of all users, divided by the user's long-term orientation.

Taking the same random user, and considering an initial median service level of 0.2964, an initial attitude of 0.5, an initial service level for the user of 0.0657, and changing the user's long-term orientation to 1, the user's attitude should decrease to $0.5 + (0.0657 - 0.2964) / 1 = 0.2693$. This can be verified by advancing by one tick.

c) Finally, the relative perception is given by the difference between the user's current service level, and the average of "remembered" previous service levels, again divided by long-term orientation. This component can similarly be tested by changing the multipliers of the two attitude components to 0, and running the simulation after setting the user's long-term orientation to 100 in order to provide a "memory" of 10 previous service levels, covering the last 100 days.

After 100 ticks, the user's service level is 0, with an attitude of 0.488, and an average of the previous service levels of 0.02979. Setting the long-term orientation back to 1, the expected new attitude would be $0.488 + (0 - 0.02979) / 1 = 0.4583$. This is verified by advancing by one tick.

As with the service level, the user attitude calculation is configured to avoid extreme values by using *min* and *max* functions to bound it in a range of 0 to 1. Similarly, since stubbornness and long-term orientation are both random user attitude parameters that are used as denominators, their initial calculation is set up to provide minimum values of 1.

8. Decide whether to pay user fee: The debugging function can be used to check the decisions of a sample of users. A sample output is:

(user 584): "My base WTP is 20309.6972951905, attitude = 0.5 and preference for waterpoints = 0.7473537977259346. So actual WTP is 7589.264702112381 and WUC fees are 2000 so I'm paying this month"

(user 579): "My base WTP is 12392.012804101649, attitude= 0.5 and preference for waterpoints = 0.29928313593582645. So actual WTP is 1854.3602262842278 and WUC fees are 2000 so I'm NOT paying this month"

In each case, the user accordingly adjusts its own money balance and the WUC's balance. The actual willingness to pay is a straightforward multiplication of the base willingness to pay, user attitude and preference for waterpoints, which are all individually bounded in the GUI or in the internal calculations in order to avoid extreme values. **Confirmed**

6.2.2. Waterpoint tests

1. Breakdown: The waterpoint breakdowns are implemented following a Weibull distribution. The distribution parameters are adjusted so that the median time between failures obtained from the literature (i.e. 60 days) corresponds to a 50% value for the cumulative distribution function (CDF), with a shape parameter of 2.5 to represent an increasing failure rate over time. Using the average values of 10 repetitions, with 20 waterpoints present in the model and disabling the HPM to evaluate the waterpoints in isolation, the following curve can be obtained over 100 days:

Figure 6-2: Comparison of theoretical Weibull distribution with model results for waterpoint breakdowns

The model results therefore provide a satisfactory fit with the expected analytical distribution. The multi-agent testing will further detail the impact of different distribution parameters. **Confirmed**

6.2.3. WUC tests

1. Update average service level: The average service level calculation of the WUC is a straightforward average of the service levels of all users under the WUC's responsibility. However, testing with different random seeds occasionally produced situations where a WUC would not by default be responsible for any users. The code was therefore modified as such:

```
Ifelse any? users with [wuc-responsible = myself]
```

```
  [set average-service-level mean [service-level] of users with [wuc-responsible = myself]]
  [set average-service-level 0]
```

Updated and confirmed

2. Assessment/repair payment: The WUC's actions in relation to the HPM are covered in the minimal model verification.

3. Fundraising: As above, this action is tested with the minimal model.

6.2.4. HPM tests

1. Priority job selection: The HPM's job selection process is dependent on the Mobiles4Water policy; if the policy is active, the report-priority-job routine reports the waterpoint which maximizes the following formula:

```
[1 / distance myself * (table:get [list-of-attitudes-towards-wucs] of myself [who] of wuc-responsible)
* breakdown-reported * (1 - breakdown-assessed)]]
```

The formula can be tested by running it on the full agentset of waterpoints, and displaying the numerical output for each waterpoint; the HPM properly selects the nearest job (adjusted for his attitude towards the WUC responsible) between the waterpoints which have been reported but

were not previously assessed. To avoid divide by zero errors, the denominator of the distance term is set to take the maximum of the actual distance, or 0.1.

For the policy case without Mobiles4Water, the formula is adjusted as follows to consider knowledge exchange through the HPM's social network, rather than directly using the waterpoints' Reported flag:

*[1 / distance myself * (table:get [list-of-attitudes-towards-wucs] of myself [who] of wuc-responsible) * (1 - table:get [knowledge-about-sources] of myself who) * (1 - breakdown-assessed)]]*

Again, the HPM selects the nearest job as a priority, but this time by only choosing between waterpoints which are known to be broken (i.e. have a value of 0) in his knowledge-about-sources list. **Confirmed**

2. Assess issue: The HPM's assessment of the priority job's status can be analysed with the debug output. As such, manipulating the priority job's status to obtain a minor breakdown results in the following output when the HPM reaches the waterpoint:

(hpm 597): "it's only a minor breakdown, I can fix it if you have the money! It costs 90000"

The HPM then queries the WUC about repair funds (which will be tested in the minimal model). However, changing the major-breakdown flag to 1 gives the following:

(hpm 597): "I can't fix this, this is a major breakdown"

The HPM then properly exits the assessment/repair routine.

3. Repair issue: Tested with the minimal model.

4. Update attitude towards WUC: Tested with the minimal model.

6.2.5. DWO tests

1. Choose major repair: The DWO's choice of a priority job for major rehabilitation can be tested by manually changing the status of a set of waterpoints. For instance, by setting the status of waterpoints 48 and 50 to 0, their assessed flag to 1, and their major breakdown flag to 1, and adjusting the knowledge-about-sources of users to reflect that the breakdowns are known, the DWO properly chooses the waterpoint with the smallest rehabilitation cost once its funds are set above the repair cost:

(dwo 598): "The IDs of waterpoints waiting for a major repair are [48 50] with a cost of [1600000 1800000]"

Similarly, the community contribution from the WUC is properly taken into account for the DWO's total repair cost:

(dwo 598): "I have fixed (waterpoint 48)! I paid 1500000. The WUC paid 100000"

The repair can be verified by checking the flags of the waterpoint (with status = 1, major-breakdown = 0, assessed = 0 and reported = 0), and by verifying that the knowledge-about-sources of the water users has been adjusted back to 1 for the waterpoints in question.

6.3. INTERACTIONS IN A MINIMAL MODEL

A minimal model can be set up by creating one agent of each type (water user, waterpoint, watersource, WUC , HPM and DWO), as illustrated below:

Figure 6-3: Minimal model configuration

First, the knowledge distribution through the social link between the user and HPM can be tested by manually setting the waterpoint's status flag to 0. The user's knowledge-about-sources table is initially:

```
{{table: [[2 1] [0 1]]}}
```

 (so that waterpoint 2 is known to have a status of 1)

After one tick, as the user attempts to reach the waterpoint, it updates its own knowledge:

```
{{table: [[2 0] [0 1]]}}
```

In parallel, the HPM's knowledge-about-sources table is then:

```
{{table: [[2 1]]}}
```

However, the following tick, its table has updated with:

```
{{table: [[2 0]]}}
```

The HPM then responds to the priority job, as tested earlier. The interaction can then be tested with the debug function, after ensuring the WUC has a sufficient money balance to proceed with repairs, and manually lowering the HPM's attitude to 0.9:

(hpm 4): "it's only a minor breakdown, I can fix it if you have the money! It costs 100000"

(wuc 3): "Here is the money, I now have 419500 left!"

(hpm 4): "I've fixed your issue! My attitude towards you has risen to 1"

The different other interaction scenarios can similarly be tested by manually adjusting the WUC's money balance. For instance, if the waterpoint was assessed but left unrepaired due to a lack of funds, increasing the WUC's balance then causes the WUC to set the waterpoint's assessed flag back to 0. The HPM then updates his priority list accordingly and proceeds with the repair at the next tick.

6.4. MULTI-AGENT TESTING

The model sub parts have been thoroughly verified in the previous sections. Therefore it is now time to run the full model and see whether all the individual decisions result into the desired results. In principle the same steps as described in the previous sections should be followed. As the debug mode has extensive output about all states, reading the storyline that's generated in debug mode in running the full model gave the confidence that the agents perform as desired. Hence, this section goes into the model variability and timeline sanity testing.

6.4.1. Model variability

The agent based model that has been created has a stochastic nature, the future states of the system are determined probabilistically. This means that (if using a different random seed) no two runs will be the same. When combining multiple runs, patterns usually emerge. To limit variability, locational setup has been fixed (see section 6.4.2).

Figure 6-4 clearly shows the stochasticity of the model results using the average user service level. The user service levels are dependent on functional and non-functional sources and can, on the moment of a breakdown, jump to another value.

Figure 6-4: Average user service level over 40 runs

Figure 6-5: Average user attitude towards WUC over 10 and 80 runs

The average user attitude towards the WUCs has a more stable pattern, as shown in Figure 6-5. This figure shows the variability in an experiment with 10 runs and with 80 runs, a smoothed curve is added to show the general pattern. Because the attitude towards the WUCs has a delay and therefore shows a more steady behaviour, this indicator will be used to check model variability. Figure 6-6 shows four box plots over time, dependent on the number of runs performed. The observation is that, although the case of 80 runs has a more outliers, the boxes don't decrease in size after approximately 40 repetitions. This can also be observed in Figure 6-7, where the standard deviation over time is shown. Finally, Figure 6-8 shows the skewness of the user attitude over time, dependent on the different amount of runs used. The skewness starts off being relatively skewed to the downside, later stabilising just under a skewness of one for all of the samples except for the one using only 10 runs.

The conclusion from the variability test is that 40 runs per model setting should be enough to get a representative sample for data analysis.

Figure 6-6: Boxplot over time, showing the variability depending on the number of runs

Figure 6-7: Standard deviation over time, dependent on number of repetitions

Figure 6-8: Skewness of user attitude over time

6.4.2. Uncertainty ranges

As shown in the previous section, the model does show some randomness. Testing where this randomness comes from can be done by fixing the random seed for the model and letting only pre-determined parts of the code remain random (using the function: `with-local-randomness`). The result of complete randomness is shown in Figure 6-9. The randomness causes the absence of emergent patterns.

Figure 6-9: Variability with full randomness

The results of the individual sources of randomness are shown in Figure 6-10. Reading the individual graphs learns that the user attitude has only little effect on the variability. The uncertainty caused by the knowledge distribution, breakdowns, social network and individual user locations does seem considerable; however, a certain trend in runs can be determined. Finally the setup of the locations of villages and waterpoints causes large variability between runs.

It can be concluded that the variability due to locational randomness causes the fact that (policy) testing is only possible with very large numbers of runs and information about the locational setup. To limit the burden of analysis the randomness surrounding the locational setup is switched of for further model use. A locational setup is chosen using the information about the district as discussed in section 2.5 (see also Figure 5-1) and will be used in the experiments of the next sections.

Figure 6-10: The effect of various sources of randomness on the user attitude towards the WUC

7. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The validated model will be used for experimentation to test what kind of behaviour emerges under different conditions. For this, a few carefully designed experiments need to be executed. This chapter describes these experiments.

7.1. EXPERIMENT DESIGN

The purpose of the experiments is to determine what kind of behaviour we can expect under which conditions. The different experiments described in the following sub-section will therefore use hypothesis in which we ask ourselves: what kind of change in behaviour do we expect if we vary certain parameters.

To limit the amount of time and resources needed to execute the experiments the experiments are split up. The effects of groups of related parameters, like parameters used to setup the social network or parameters related with income and payments are tested separately using scenario spaces. In this way it's possible to see the effects of the combination of parameters on the selected KPIs. The full factorial parameter sweep that is built into NetLogo is used to execute the experiments.

Because the model created is highly complex and therefore takes a long time to run it's important to choose the time frame wisely. To test long run system performance but still keep the simulation time within reasonable limits, the model is run for 730 ticks, which represents 2 years in the real world. One run takes approximately 1 minute.

As the behaviour and parametric adjustments of the model are highly dependent on the location of the users, the clean waterpoints, dirty water sources and hand pump mechanics (HPM), it has been decided that the locational setup has a fixed random seed. This random seed has been chosen in such a way that the resulting spatial distribution represents a typical Ugandan rural area, as described in section 2.4. Other variables that determine the spatial distribution like the number of users, waterpoints, distances between these two, etc. have also been fixed and the effect of varying these is not tested.

7.2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experiment descriptions below only specify the variables that are varied during that particular test, the variables that are not under study in the particular test are fixed on their reference setting. These settings are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Parameter settings reference model

Variable	Value
Mobiles 4 Water system	Off
Number of clean waterpoints	20
Fraction of dirty water sources	0.8 (so 16 dirty sources)
Maximum distance between user and waterpoint	2.2 km
Number of population clusters	15
Users per cluster	36
Max radius from cluster	0.9 km

Base willingness to pay	3000 shilling
WUC-Monthly payment	600 shilling
Number of HPMS	1
Max radius for WUC	1.6 km
Chance of global link	20%
Total social links per user	15
Social network local radius	1 km
Daily social interaction	With 15% of social links
Relative effect of social interaction	1
Relative effect of change in service level	1
Relative effect of absolute service level	0.5
HPM attitude increment	0.2
HPM negative experience bias	1.5
Major breakdown interval	1825 days
Minor breakdown interval	60 days
Weibull shape parameter	2.5

Next to the parameters that are used for the test, the following parameters are selected as KPIs and therefore saved as model output:

- Mean user attitude towards WUC
- Mean user service level
- Mean HPM response time
- Mean waterpoint down time
- Number of non-functional waterpoints
- Number of users with service level = 0

7.2.1. Social network experiment

The effects of the parameters used to setup the social network on overall system performance are tested with the following experiment:

Setup:

- Repetitions per combination [20]: In order to limit analysis burden

Parameter settings:

- See Table 4.

Full factorial parameter sweep:

- Chance of global link [0.1 0.2 0.3]
- Total social links per user [8 12 16 20]
- Social network local radius [5 10 15]
- Daily social interaction [0.05 0.15 0.25]

The expectation is that a larger social network with more social interaction will lead to quicker knowledge diffusion about non-functional waterpoints resulting in faster HPM response time and higher user service levels.

7.2.2. User attitude adjustment experiment

The users adjust their attitude towards their WUC on 3 separate factors:

- the attitude of the users on the other side of the social-links
- their difference between their current and historic service levels
- the difference between their start (base) and current service level

The relative effects of these three influence is tested using the following experimental setup:

Setup:

- Repetitions per combination [20]: In order to limit analysis burden

Parameter settings:

- See Table 4.

Full factorial parameter sweep:

- Relative effect of social network [0.50 0.75 1.00 1.25 1.50]
- Relative effect of relative perception [0.50 0.75 1.00 1.25 1.50]
- Relative effect of absolute perception [0.25 0.50 0.75 1.00 1.25 1.50]

In this case there are no expectations about the differences in behaviour, therefore we will test the effects of these parameters and then try to explain the resulting changes with the knowledge about the model.

7.2.3. Income and payments experiment

The user willingness to pay for the maintenance of waterpoints is calculated by dividing the user income by the base willingness to pay (which is equal to the average income). The effects of the base willingness to pay and the height of the monthly payment are tested in the following experiment:

Setup:

- Repetitions per combination [20]: In order to limit analysis burden

Parameter settings:

- See Table 4.

Full factorial parameter sweep:

- Base willingness to pay [2000 4000]: with steps of 200
- WUC monthly payment [300 1000]: with steps of 100

The expectation is that a lower willingness to pay results in lower water service levels as there is no money to be able to maintain the sources. A too low monthly WUC fee would have the same results, but a too high fee might lead to a decrease in paying users, also resulting in the fact that there is too little money to maintain the sources.

7.2.4. Mobiles 4 Water experiment

When the HPM finds out about a non-functional source, he will travel to the waterpoint and start interaction with the water user committee (WUC). The 'base' model uses the social network to distribute knowledge about functional and non-functional sources. Dependent on the degree of interconnectedness between the HPM and the water users of a non-functional waterpoint it takes some time for the knowledge to diffuse in such a way that it reaches the HPM. The Mobiles 4 Water system enables both the users and the WUCs to update information about waterpoints in a central system that the HPM is also able to access. This should result into faster HPM responses, shorter times to repair and higher service levels. An experiment testing the effectiveness of M4W will be executed under the following conditions:

Setup:

- Repetitions per combination [40]

Parameter settings:

- See Table 4.

Full factorial parameter sweep:

- Mobile for water system [on off]

The expectation is that the Mobiles 4 Water system has a positive effect on the repair times and user service levels.

7.2.5. Sanitation policy experiment

The use of dirty water sources is a known issue in rural Africa. Many users do not know that various diseases, like cholera, are spread through contaminated drinking water. Therefore the effect of a policy to increase the preference for clean waterpoints is tested. In the base model users decide about their water source dependent on the cleanliness of the waterpoint multiplied by the preference for clean water (uniformly distributed between 0 and 1) and divided by the distance. The following experiment is used to test the effect of a higher preference for clean water, by setting the minimum threshold for preference for clean water to 0.2. This parameter then retains a uniform distribution between 0.2 and 1, and aims to simulate a targeted education campaign that could be aimed at the users least sensitive to their water quality.

Setup:

- Repetitions per combination [40]

Parameter settings:

- See Table 4.

Full factorial parameter sweep:

- Preference for clean water [uniform(0.0 - 1.0) uniform(0.2 - 1.0)]

The expectation is that more people will choose for clean water sources and service level will increase. On the other hand there is also the possibility that people choose waterpoints that are so far away that their service level will also be 0 (distance larger than 1.5 km).

8. ANALYSING DATA

The data gathered from the experiments described in section 7.2 will be used to analyse model behaviour. Relatively simple graphs have been used in order provide maximum understand ability and readability. The results of the different tests are presented in the sections below.

8.1. SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS

The social network analysis was done in order to see what the influence of the parameters to setup the social network is on the service level and the HPM response time. Figure 8-1 shows the effects of the amount of global links and total links on the service level over time. A smoothed line is added to show the general trend of the data. It seems that the amount of global links does not influence the service level while especially a high amount of total links has a positive effect on the service level. Figure 8-2 shows the effects of the local radius and daily social interaction on the HPM response time. The response time does not seem influenced by the local radius but a small social interaction seems to have a large (negative) effect on system performance.

Figure 8-1: Effect of global links (top) and total amount of links (bottom) on service level

Figure 8-2: Effect of local radius (top) and daily social interaction (bottom) on HPM response times

Figure 8-3 shows the distribution of the average service level and HPM response time over the entire run time. The first row shows the dependency on the amount of global links. From the graphs it seems that this has little influence. Secondly the effect of total links is shown; especially the situation with 20 social links seems to result into way better system performance. The third row shows the effect of different local radii, a parameter that also seems to be non-influential. Finally the result of varying the social interaction between users is displayed; here it's obvious that the low interaction rates result in lower system performance.

Figure 8-3: The effect of social network parameters on service level (left) and HPM response time (right)

Some differences in system performance can be observed from Figure 8-3, as most results do not show normal distributions (using Kolmogorov-Smirnov), the statistical difference needs to be tested with a Kruskal-Wallis test. The results are shown in Table 5. The observations were correct, only the total number of links and daily social interaction have a significant influence on service level and HPM response time. To further test which of the subsets of parameters result in significant differences a post-hoc test needs to be performed. For this however the samples need to be normally distributed. Although this is not the case using our limited number of results, we assume that they are normally distributed in order to be able to finish the analysis. The results of the post hoc test for the total number of social links and the daily social interaction are shown in Table 6 and Table 7 respectively, the significant results are bolted.

It can be concluded that there the total amount of social links and the daily interaction have a significant impact on the system performance. More specifically, a large number of links improves the system performance while little social interaction decreases the system performance. Without the Mobiles 4 Water system in place the service level is very dependent on the social interaction between water users, which is not desirable due to its unpredictability.

Table 5: Results of Kruskal-Wallis test for social network parameters

Parameter	user service level	HPM response time
Percentage of global links	No significant difference	No significant difference
Number of total links	Significant difference ***	Significant difference ***
Local radius	No significant difference	No significant difference
Daily social interaction	Significant difference ***	Significant difference ***
Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1		

Table 6: Significance of differences in average service level dependent on the number of social links

Difference between total number of social links	Significance service level	Significance HPM response time
8-12	0.0772	0.2869
8-16	0.0014	0.3369
8-20	0.0000	0.0000
12-16	0.5867	0.9997
12-20	0.0000	0.0000
16-20	0.0000	0.0000

Table 7: Significance of differences in average service level dependent on the daily social interaction (post-hoc test)

Difference daily social interaction	Significance service level	Significance HPM response time
0.05 – 0.10	0.0000	0.0000
0.05 – 0.15	0.0000	0.0000
0.10 – 0.15	0.0000	0.0057

The effect of both significant parameters combined on the service level can be seen in Figure 8-4, only the smoothed line is given for the sake of readability.

Figure 8-4: Facet grid effect on service level with differences in total links and social interaction

8.2. USER ATTITUDE ADJUSTMENT ANALYSIS

The user attitude towards the functioning of the WUC is influenced by the attitude of their social network, the difference between their historic average service level and the current service level compared to the mean service level at the start of the model runs. All these influences have a multiplier to represent their relative influence. The experiment set out to test how the variance in these relative influences affects the attitude towards the WUC and the system behaviour in general.

Figure 8-5 shows the effects of the different relative influences on the average user attitude towards the WUC, the maximum is one (positive) and the minimum is 0 (negative). It shows that the effect of changing the relative influence of the social network (top) and relative perception (middle) has little influence. The effect of the difference between the base service level and the actual service level seems to have the biggest influence. Low values for relative influence of base service level result in the fact that the attitude does not really increase while higher relative influences cause the attitude to rise in the beginning but then flatten of. The highest attitudes are achieved with medium level importance of base service levels.

Figure 8-5: Effect of relative importance of social (top), historic (middle) and base (bottom) influence on attitude towards WUC

Figure 8-6 shows a more detailed analysis of the end state mean attitude towards the WUC. In contradiction to what Figure 8-5 showed it seems that a higher relative importance of the base service level in general leads to higher attitudes towards the WUC. However, higher importance of the base service level also leads to more runs ending up with very low attitudes towards the WUC. It seems that runs with a few negative experiences lead to very low attitudes, in other words: higher relative importance of the difference between base service level and actual service level has a polarizing effect.

As the end states shown in Figure 8-6 have more runs ending up on either the low or the high end of the attitude towards the WUC, a normal distribution cannot be assumed. Therefore ANOVA cannot be performed and the Kruskal-Wallis test is selected. The test shows that both the relative influence of the social network (significance = 0.00) and the base service level (significance 0.00) have a significant effect on the user attitude towards the WUCs, the effect of the importance of historic service levels is non-significant. Due to the fact that distributions are not normal (values show multiple peaks in the result on both sides of the graphs), a post hoc test will not be performed in this case.

Figure 8-6: End state user attitude towards WUC for different relative influence of base service level

The conclusion is that, if people in Uganda are mostly influenced by their base water service level, an increase or decrease in service levels might quickly deteriorate the user attitude towards the WUCs. It's therefore important that as soon as the WUCs are installed, they are performing well. Obviously, this is an exploratory approach towards the influence of different factors on people's attitude adjustments, further research about the exact dynamics are necessary to more clearly be able to define the effects of these attitude adjustment to the system.

8.3. INCOME AND PAYMENT ANALYSIS

The income and payment experiments were performed in order to find out what the effects of the monthly water fees and peoples willingness to pay for these water services on the system performance. In the model, every month people decide whether they want to pay the monthly fee. If the willingness to pay multiplied by the attitude towards the WUC and the preference for clean waterpoints (both between 0 and 1) is higher than the monthly payment, the payment is transferred to the WUC, who is then able to pay for assessments and repairs.

Figure 8-7 shows the amount of dysfunctional waterpoints depending on the monthly payment and the willingness to pay. The figure shows that, obviously, high payments and high willingness to pay lead to low amount of dysfunctional waterpoints. A high monthly payment with low willingness to pay leads directly to money shortages with the WUCs and therefore directly increases the non-functional waterpoints. In the case of too low payments, the increase in broken waterpoints is last steep as in the beginning the WUCs still have enough resources to pay for the repairs, with low

incomes, this situation is not sustainable and the amount of non-functional waterpoints decreases gradually.

Figure 8-8 shows a heat map where the colours represent the service level at the end of the runs. The same trend can be observed. Although high monthly payments combined with high willingness to pay lead to good results, the risk of having high too high payments which result into people not paying is also high. If willingness to pay is low, a relatively low payment (at least able to keep some of the sources functional) seems to be the safest solution.

The hypothesis from the experiment description can be confirmed: Lower willingness to pay results in lower water service levels as there is no money to be able to maintain the sources. A too low monthly WUC fee would have the same results, but a too high fee might lead to a decrease in paying users, also resulting in the fact that there is too little money to maintain the sources.

Figure 8-7: Effect of monthly payment (horizontal) and willingness to pay (vertical) on the amount of dysfunctional waterpoints

Figure 8-8: Effect of monthly payment (horizontal) and willingness to pay (vertical) on the average run service level

8.4. MOBILES 4 WATER POLICY ANALYSIS

As described in the previous sections, a mobile phone system to report broken waterpoints called Mobiles 4 Water (M4W) is recently implemented to increase the speed of repairs and through that the water service levels. All the previous tests were executed without the existence of the Mobile 4 Water system. This section sees into the effect of the mobile phone system on overall performance.

Figure 8-9 shows the effects of M4W on three different KPIs: the average service level, the amount of people with service level 0 and the average down time of waterpoints (time it takes from down time to repair). The M4W is only turned on after step 180 to allow the model to start up. As expected, it seems that M4W has a positive effect on both the service level and the average down times of waterpoints.

Figure 8-9: Effect of M4W system on water service level (top), people with service level 0 (centre) and down time (bottom)

The effects of the M4W system on the run averages for service level and down time can be seen in Figure 8-10. The positive effect of M4W is clearly visible. The significance needs to be tested using statistical tests.

Looking at the distribution we cannot directly say whether they come from a normal distribution. A Shapiro-Wilk test (because of relatively small sample) shows that both the service levels and the down times cannot be regarded as normally distributed. Therefore a Kruskal-Wallis test needs to be performed on both variables. The results shows that the M4W system has a significant positive influence on the service level (sig. 0.00) and waterpoint down time (sig. 0.00).

Combining the results of the statistical test and the graphical observations, the conclusion is that M4W has a positive influence on system performance.

Figure 8-10: Effect of M4W on the average service level (top) and the average down time (bottom)

8.5. SANITATION POLICY ANALYSIS

The other policy option is educating people about the dangers of using water from non-official water sources. This would hopefully lead people to be pickier about the source they are using and lead to more users choosing clean sources. The effects of this policy on the model are shown in this section.

Figure 8-11 shows the effect of the sanitation policy on average service level, the amount of users with service level 0 and the amount of people using dirty sources. The sanitation policy seems to be highly effective. The average service levels are higher and less people use dirty sources. Furthermore, the expectation that the number of people having a service level of 0 would go up due to higher travelling distances does not seem to materialise.

As can be seen in Figure 8-12 the policy is highly effective, it shows the run averages for both policies. What can be seen is that the sanitation policy leads to high service levels, with a small standard deviation compared to the runs where the sanitation policy was not implemented. The same holds for the amount of users using dirty sources (which is low due to the policy). A Kruskal-Wallis test (Shapiro-Wilk test rejects normal distribution) confirms the significance of the difference in performance due to the sanitation policy (sig. 0.00 for both service level as down time).

It can be concluded raising the preference for clean water, which can be reached through informing people about the dangers of dirty water sources, has a positive effect on the system behaviour.

Figure 8-11: The effect of sanitation policy on service level (top) amount of people with service level 0 and the amount of people using dirty sources (bottom)

Figure 8-12: The effect of sanitation policy on average service levels (left) and number of people using dirty sources (right)

9. MODEL VALIDATION

Model validation is the process of assessing whether the model can be used for the purpose it was built for: gaining more insight into the dynamics of a complex system or answering a specific research question. Multiple methods for validation are available and include checking the model with historic behaviour, expert (face) validation and comparing the model outcomes with available literature from other fields.

9.1. EXPERT VALIDATION

Model validation is not a single action; it should be performed throughout the modelling process, to ensure that the model under construction will fit its needs. Therefore numerous conversations and discussions have been held with the problem owner, Deirdre Casella. This resulted in extensive feedback on all assumptions made during the creation of the agent based model and significantly improved the quality of the work.

Just before the verification stage (when the modelling was thought to be finished) a meeting was held at the International Water House in The Hague. Here multiple experts from the rural water supply domain were either physically or digitally present (1 calling in from Uganda, 1 calling from Bangladesh). During the meeting, the main model assumptions were presented and some model runs were executed. This obviously caused some enthusiasm but also a large stream of feedback on different model assumptions and results. Some of which were not deemed important enough to incorporate as it would not change the model behaviour. Other issues were risen but no solutions were available: for instance, the combination of the cost of sending sms messages to the central system, the income levels, the willingness to pay and the monthly water fees are important model parameters, however, actual decisions made by people spending their limited incomes is much more complex, this complexity could not be translated into formal decision rules within the scope of this project.

However, some feedback was considered important and feasible enough to spend extra modelling time on. First of all, the stakeholders would appreciate to be able to run the model without the Mobiles 4 Water system. In this way the performance of the Mobile 4 Water system can be compared to not having M4W in place. This required us to use the social network to also distribute knowledge about functional and non-functional sources. Secondly, some assumptions about the spatial distribution were rejected, a new locational setup was created that was more based on population clusters with waterpoints placed in and around the clusters. Finally, the service level was not calculated appropriately, instead of being linearly dependent on the distance and the 'cleanliness' of a source the service level now is calculated using the assumption presented in section 2.4.

Because this large step in validation was already made before the verification, the verification and experiments are based on the model that includes the improvements made after the feedback session. If desired by the stakeholder, another feedback session, now looking more at the outcomes could lead to even more improvements.

9.2. HISTORIC REPLAY

Historic replay validation tries to fit outcomes to historic data. If the model outcomes are able to replicate what has happened in the past, the model is deemed valid. Currently, no data about the functioning of M4W is available to the modellers. However, because the M4W system comes with a

monitoring system and a central server where data is stored, it might be possible to use historic replay validation in the future. On the other hand, data about day to day user service levels and attitudes towards individual water user committees will most likely not be recorded in the near future while these factors are highly important in the functioning of the system. This makes it more difficult to use data to validate the full model.

9.3. LITERATURE COMPARISON

A literature comparison validates the model by comparing the model outcomes with existing literature. If the literature provides the same conclusions as the model does, the confidence in the validity of the model grows. Due to time constraints, further research into conclusions other reports was not possible, therefore the validation relies mainly on the extensive expert validation that was performed. However, it can be stated that the method of using agent based models to research rural water supply is an effective approach and improves upon the static mental models that decision makers often base their decisions on (Pahl-Wostl, 2002).

10. USING MODEL RESULTS

The past chapters have presented the entire process of the modelling cycle. This final chapter discusses how the model results can be used by providing the final conclusions and giving some recommendations. Finally the model limitations and possibilities for future work will shortly be discussed.

10.1. CONCLUSIONS

This project set out to gain more insights into the inner workings of the Mobiles 4 Water system and the reason for the fact that the system does not function in an optimal way. Over the course of the modelling project, various insights have been gained. Some of which were already gained during the model formalisation, others followed from the experimentation with the model.

First of all, the modelled system seems to have an important feedback structure. People with low service levels are less likely to pay for a water point, resulting in low WUC incomes and therefore little funds for maintenance. This will over time lead to dysfunctional waterpoints, lowering people's service levels even more. An important improvement is therefore to make water users understand that waterpoints need to be maintained and that this maintenance cost money. Without this money, none of the waterpoints would be functional. Besides, people need to understand that water user committees (WUCs) are not private companies who make a profit, but only spend the user fees on operational expenses. If a waterpoint is not performing well, this is not a reason for withholding the monthly fee; instead, it should be an incentive to pay more in order to collect enough money for repairs. This being said, it is also important that the WUCs are trusted enough, which can only be reached by the acts of the WUCs themselves.

Related to this are the heights of the user fees, setting fees too low results in low maintenance levels and lower service levels over time, however high fees also pose a risk of money shortage due to the fact that people do not have the money to pay their contribution. All in all, the WUCs might need some help in setting the correct user fees; high enough to ensure sustainable operation, which requires a long term vision that often lacks in rural Africa (Hofstede, Hofstede, & Minkov, 1991), but not so high that people are not able to pay. Concepts such as payments dependent on income levels might be necessary to keep service levels high while loosening burden on the poorest.

The social network has a strong influence on service levels in systems where there is no system like Mobiles 4 Water. Strong and active social networks lead to fast knowledge diffusion and higher service levels. However, the functioning of a social network is too dependent on unpredictable parameters such as the number of connections, the location of those connections and the amount of social interaction between users from their own villages and especially the social interaction between villages (as HPMs will usually not live in the same village). Being dependent on these uncertainties for something vital as the daily water supply is not desired.

Therefore, a system like Mobiles 4 Water is preferred over letting knowledge diffusion depend upon the social network. Mobiles 4 Water does show significant improvements in service levels and lowers the average time it takes to repair dysfunctional waterpoints. Higher service levels make people more willing to pay user fees, keeping the waterpoints function over longer periods of time. Hence, Mobiles 4 Water contributes to a more sustainable rural water supply.

Finally, because users do not consider using non-verified water sources to be problematic they switch to these dirty sources as soon as their own waterpoint breaks down. As service levels are

highly dependent on the 'cleanliness' of a water source this has a large influence on the measured service levels. Educating people about the fact that using contaminated water causes serious diseases is therefore highly recommended. The analysis shows that although people might need to travel further to find a functional clean source, the overall service level does increase significantly, even if only the people who consider the quality of their water extremely important are addressed. Seeing the importance of clean water will at the same time induce more people to contribute to the payments, put more trust in functional WUCs and be more willing to send text messages to the M4W system.

10.2. MODEL LIMITATIONS

Agent based modelling is a new and innovative technique which, although many show an above average interest, is mostly unknown to many of the stakeholders involved in the M4W project. NetLogo provides visually attractive output and therefore the danger lies in people being impressed with all the beautiful images that are shown when the model is run. In addition, the output of various runs can be converted into beautiful graphs that might seduce the reader in accepting all model outcomes as the truth. For this reason a few model limitations are being presented here.

First and foremost, in any computer simulated model, every single line of code is an assumption. Accordingly, every model is not more than a set of assumptions about a real world system, with all its endless complexities. User decisions about sending an sms to a central number are presented as simple decision rules while sometimes these little and seemingly unimportant decisions have a lot of dependencies in real life. Consequently, all model results can only be interpreted keeping in mind all the assumptions given in the formalisation in section 3 and 4.

Finally, the presented model was created as a part of a Master course with the goal of getting to know the entire process of creating an agent based model, it has been programmed by modellers with no prior experience with AB models. The utmost care is taken while creating and verifying the model, however, some beginner errors might have been made in the process.

10.3. FUTURE WORK

For this modelling exercise, some deliberate choices have been made by the modellers. The decision was made to look at the M4W system from a local perspective, leaving out larger governmental organisations. Because of the complexity of the agents' interactions within the model, it was only feasible to let the model run for 730 ticks (2 years), therefore excluding long term developments such as the implementation of new waterpoints.

As already mentioned in the model limitation section, human decisions are not easily replicated within a formal model, especially if the modellers are not familiar with the local culture. During interactions with the stakeholders, interesting examples of cultural differences came to the table. For instance: a water user committee might not dare to collect money from some users because of their high social status. To accurately represent all the complex structures that are present in rural Uganda, more field research is required.

Due to time and hardware constraints, it was not possible to do a parameter sweep over all parameters at the same time. As the model showed reasonably large variation between runs, large amounts of runs were necessary before being able to draw valid conclusions. This, in combination with the complexity of interaction and large number of parameters, resulted in the fact that a lot of time and processing power were necessary to do the limited amount of runs presented in this report. A more extensive analysis would include full factorial sweeps over parameters using smaller steps

between parameter sets; this would enable the modellers to find tipping points in behaviour more accurately.

An improvement over the used method might be to use the EMA workbench (Kwakkel & Pruyt, 2013) to test the model under deep uncertainty (Lempert, Popper, & Bankes, 2003). The advantage is that the EMA workbench is able to use techniques such as Latin Hypercube sampling, which cannot be used in NetLogo. Using model runs in which large combinations of parameters were varied, the patient rule induction method (PRIM) can be used to further analyse model results. However, due to the model variability in runs with the same parameter settings, the use of Latin Hypercube sampling is not straight forward and would also require many repetitions.

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Appendix A NETLOGO MODEL INTERFACE

number-of-waterpoints 20

max-waterpoint-distance 22

fraction-of-dirty-watersources 0.8

number-of-population-clusters 15

users-per-cluster 36

max-r radius-from-cluster 9.0

base-willingness-to-pay 3000

wuc-monthly-payment 600

number-of-HPMs 1

max-r radius-for-wuc 16

On debug On M4W

On draw-waterpoints? On profiler-switch

On graphs

Money for DWO

Money for WUCs

User-colors
Knowledge-distribution (WPS)

ticks: 0

3D

% of population with access
78.56

% of paying users
0

Social network

p_global 0.20

total-links 15

local-radius 10

daily-social-interaction 0.15

Attitude increments

effect-of-social-network 1.5

effect-of-relative-perception 1.5

effect-of-absolute-perception 0.75

attitude-increment 0.3

negative-experience-bias 1.5

Breakdown interval

major-breakdown-interval 1795

minor-breakdown-interval 60

weibull-shape-parameter 2.5

Histogram for distant links of...

Average attitude of users

Histogram for total links of us...

Histogram for attitude of use...

Avg. service level of users

Attitudes towards WUCs of H...

Histogram for service level o...

Avg last downtime of waterp...

DWO balance

Percentage of functioning wa...

WUC balance

